

Code of Conduct for the Human-Centered and Ethical Development of Immersive Technologies

Co-authors: Rosemarie de la Cruz Bernabe, Rigmor C. Baraas, Michael Barngrover, Shereen Cox, Lene A. Hagen, Alina Kadlubsky, Panagiotis Kavouras, Ieva Krastina, Miltos Ladikas, Melissa Amoros Lark, Marco Correa Pérez, Lucas Stephane, Oliver Schreer

Contributors: Leon Kester, Faisal Mushtaq, Franziska Sörgel, Cristiana-Anca Voinov, Eleni Spyrakou

Reviewers: Subject to several iterative reviews informed by consultations with XR experts (developers, policymakers, researchers), the Consortium, and the public.

This document is aspirational in scope and co-created to provide guidance for developers of XR technologies. While some provisions may intersect with legal considerations, the document itself does not carry legally binding force.

2025

Consortium

XR4HUMAN (The Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR) is a three-year European Commission Horizon-funded project. Its mission is to co-create living guidance documents on ethical and related policy, regulatory, governance, and interoperability issues of XR technologies whilst building public trust and acceptance and a strong and competitive European XR ecosystem. The consortium includes 12 partners from eight countries.

No	Role	Name	Country
1	Coordinator	Universitetet i Sørøst-Norge	Norway
2	Co-Lead	Universitetet i Oslo	Norway
3	Partner	Institutt for Energiteknikk	Norway
4	Partner	Norges Teknisk-Naturvitenskapelige Universitet	Norway
5	Partner	National Technical University of Athens	Greece
6	Partner	Universiteit Leiden	Netherlands
7	Partner	Karlsruher Institut für Technologie	Denmark
8	Partner	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V.	Germany
9	Partner	Open AR Cloud Europe	Germany
10	Partner	University of Leeds	United Kingdom
11	Partner	Stichting Fontys	Netherlands
12	Partner	XR4Europe	Belgium

Deliverable leads: University of Oslo and University of South-East Norway

Grant Agreement No.101070155

Preamble

This Code of Conduct (henceforth, Code) sets forth the ethical obligations for everyone involved in technological innovation and governance of immersive or extended reality (XR) technologies, including Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), Mixed Reality (MR), as well as all current and other emerging and future technologies. This Code represents a statement of shared ethical values and responsibilities, written in consultation with academics, developers, and governmental agencies. It aims to set out a shared understanding of respect for human rights, protection of user privacy, promotion of inclusivity, and safeguarding of the mental, physical, and social well-being of all users. This Code applies to designers, developers, providers, and all XR industry stakeholders involved in the lifecycle of immersive technologies. The principles outlined here serve as a guide for creating immersive experiences that are ethical, inclusive, safe, and aligned with human rights standards.

Guiding Principles

Human-Centered Design

- Ensure that the needs, values, and well-being of users are guiding considerations in all stages of development.
- Ensure immersive technologies enhance user agency, allowing users to make informed decisions and control their digital interactions, avoiding deceptive techniques or manipulative design.

Diversity, Inclusivity, Accessibility and Equitability

- Design immersive experiences that are inclusive and accessible to a diverse range of users, considering the intended use. Aim to reflect the needs of underrepresented, marginalised and vulnerable populations, including people with disabilities and the economically disadvantaged.
- Aim to foster fairness in immersive technologies while avoiding the reinforcement of existing or new inequalities.

Trustworthiness and Transparency

- Maintain transparency throughout the design, development, and deployment of immersive technologies, particularly regarding data collection, processing, usage, retention, and destruction.
- Provide clear and understandable communication about the digital and non-digital nature of immersive environments, such as in AR and MR technologies.

Privacy and Data Governance

- Respect user and bystander privacy and implement robust personal data protection measures.
- Inform users explicitly, in a manner that is understandable, and at predefined and reasonable intervals about the collection, usage, and sharing of their data, especially in cases involving third-party providers.

Safe Experience

- Design immersive experiences to prevent harm to users and bystanders, including protection mechanisms against manipulation, abuse, and harassment.
- Develop and implement content moderation and community guidelines that promote safe and respectful behaviour.

Identity and Right to Anonymity

- Allow users to own and control their identities, personas, and avatars, both during the users' lifetime and after death, with the ability to customize and transport them across platforms, ensuring continuity and interoperability.
- Respect user preferences for anonymity.

Sustainability

- Minimise the environmental impact of immersive technologies by promoting sustainable practices in their design, development and deployment, focusing on reducing energy consumption and waste.

Technical Security and Interoperability

- Ensure the security of essential technical processes, such as digitally mediating functions, to prevent data breaches, hijacking and manipulation of the immersive experience by malicious entities.
- Foster the development of standards that allow for interoperability between different platforms and devices, enabling seamless transitions of digital identities and assets.

Moral Dilemma Resolution and Risk Management

- Engage all relevant stakeholders when developing procedures for moral dilemma resolution and traceable risk management.
- Guarantee clear traceable responsibilities, ensuring that developers and providers are identifiable and accountable to warrant ethical and legal responses in the event of harm, abuse, or misuse.

Article 1: User Transparency by Design

1. Clear Purpose Statement: Developers should include an easily accessible description of the application, its purpose, and features including compliance with this Code. Developers should specify who the application is designed for, the target demographics, and the specific user needs it addresses, to help users determine if the product is suitable for them.

2. Accessibility Limitations: Developers should outline any known limitations related to accessibility. This should be clearly communicated to set appropriate user expectations.

3. Risk Information: Developers should clearly communicate risks, uncertainties, or limitations associated with the technologies, especially regarding privacy, data usage, safety, or the robustness and reliability of features.

4. User Guide: Adequate resources, guidance and help should be provided to offer the full context and explain how specific features operate.

5. User Data Transparency: Developers should be explicit about what the application does with user data. Inform users clearly and frequently, if possible, at predefined intervals, about the collection, usage and sharing of their data, especially in cases involving third-party providers (cf. Article 2).

5. User Feedback and Problem Reporting: Developers should establish a clear and accessible process for users to report problems, suggest improvements, or provide feedback on the application. This ensures ongoing improvement and responsiveness to user needs.

Article 2: Data Protection and Privacy by Design

1. Designing Privacy-Sensitive Experiences: Privacy as a core consideration should be integrated into every phase of design of immersive technologies. Wherever feasible, data should be processed on-device to reduce dependence on cloud-based solutions and minimise exposure to security risks.

2. Respect for Bystanders: Developers should account for the rights to privacy and lawful personal data processing of bystanders who may be inadvertently captured or involved in the immersive experiences of others. Developers should take measures to protect bystanders' privacy and make all reasonable efforts to inform them of any relevant impacts.

3. Empowerment Tools: Provide users with intuitive tools to manage their privacy settings and access to clear information about how their data is being used and shared. Information should be provided in multiple formats — such as audio, video, and at varying levels of language proficiency — to be comprehensible to the broadest range of users.

4. *Respecting Data Rights:* Respect users' rights to their personal data, including the right to access and delete their data. Developers should clearly indicate types of data (e.g., biometric data, sensitive personal data etc.) and the rights associated with each type.

Article 3: Risk Management by Design

1. *Risk Management and Communication:* Developers should continuously and sufficiently assess and transparently mitigate risks related to data security, privacy breaches, and critical vulnerabilities in the immersive technology experience. Developers or Data Controllers should make users aware of whether and how their personal data and other data captured could be or has been misused or compromised.

2. *Promote Sustainable Practices:* Developers should promote sustainable practices in the design, development, and deployment of immersive experiences to minimise negative impacts and promote efficiency during the product lifecycle.

3. *Risk of Obsolescence:* Developers should make all reasonable efforts to extend the horizon of obsolescence to prolong and support schemes for repair, reuse, and recycling

4. *Establishing and Adopting Standards Across Industries:* Developers should use open and widely supported file formats and utilise metadata and annotate frameworks that enhance content discovery and accessibility. Developers should adopt and advance interoperability across platforms, systems, processes, workflows, and industries, including integration of existing and future standards.

Article 4: Well-being by Design

1. *Promote & Support Well-being:* Developers should design immersive experiences that uphold the mental and physical well-being of users. Customisable (personalised) ergonomic design features should be built into the experience. This is to encourage users to engage in healthier behaviours and time management, such as taking breaks, limiting screen time, avoiding prolonged and/or uncomfortable physical actions, and maintaining awareness of their physical surroundings.

2. *Safety Features:* Developers should implement features that support user safety. This includes taking reasonable steps to mitigate potential risks associated with overuse, addiction, physical strain (e.g., visual discomfort, muscle or joint strain), or disembodiment. This could be supported by time and usage monitoring, combined with adaptive suggestions based on age, gender, or other characteristics.

3. *Special Protections for Vulnerable Groups:* Developers should include special considerations for children and other vulnerable persons¹ including those with limited digital proficiency, ensuring that immersive content is appropriate and fosters a safe and inclusive experience.

Article 5: Identity, personas and avatars

1. *Identity, Persona & Avatar Ownership:* Developers should ensure that users have control over relevant elements of their identities, personas and avatars to the extent feasible within the platform's commercial operations. Users should be able to transfer their avatars across platforms.

2. *Special Protections for Children and Other Vulnerable Groups:* Developers should include specific safeguards to protect children and other vulnerable groups, ensuring that their online presence is secure and free from exploitation.

3. *Prevention of Identity, Persona and Avatar Theft:* Developers should implement robust security measures to protect users from identity, persona and avatar theft, including unauthorised use or replication of their personas and avatars. This includes mechanisms such as multi-factor authentication, secure user verification, and alerts for suspicious activity. Developers are encouraged to follow industry best practices for user protection to safeguard users against impersonation and misuse of their identities, personas and avatars.

4. *Appropriate Avatar Customisation:* User should have access to diverse and inclusive customisation options when creating their avatars allowing for diverse self-representation. Developers should implement safeguards to discourage the creation of avatars that may be harmful, offensive, or cause distress to others. This includes following standards for avatar customisation that discourage disturbing representations depending on context. Developers should offer avatar moderation tools, community policies, and reporting features that allow users to flag inappropriate avatars, triggering corrective action when necessary.

¹ Directive 2013/33/EU defines vulnerable persons to include the following: “minors, unaccompanied minors, disabled people, elderly people, pregnant women, single parents with minor children, victims of trafficking in human beings, persons with serious illnesses, persons with mental disorders and persons who have been subjected to torture, rape or other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence, such as victims of female genital mutilation”

Article 6: Shared Spaces

- 1. Community Guidelines:* Developers should establish clear community guidelines for acceptable behaviour (such as refraining from profanities) within shared immersive spaces. These guidelines should be designed to promote respect, inclusivity, and safety for all participants.
- 2. Content Moderation:* Developers should be responsible for implementing robust moderation tools that allow for the prevention and/or removal of abusive or harmful content in shared immersive environments.
- 3. Private and Public Spaces:* Developers should design clear distinctions between private and public spaces within immersive environments, ensuring users understand the implications of engaging in each type of space. Users should have control over their level of visibility and interaction in shared environments. For example, developers should clearly communicate whether invisible observers or any form of recording are allowed and provide users with the option to opt out or adjust their settings accordingly. This transparency helps users make informed decisions about their participation and privacy in shared digital environments.
- 4. Transparency of Roles:* Developers should clearly and frequently inform users regarding the entities and persons who have authority to make changes, moderate, or control the space, along with an accessible history of such actions.
- 5. Transparency of Experience:* Developers should clearly and frequently communicate the differences in users' experience, including but not limited to differences based on users' access to devices (e.g., mobile, PC, HMDs, wearables, glasses and other devices such as trackers, gloves and suits) to ensure all participants are aware of the variations in affordances and experiences.
- 6. Transparency of Actions:* Developers should ensure that actions that may be invisible to other users, such as recording or capturing screenshots, are clearly signalled to all users.
- 7. Transparency of Digitally Mediated Processes:* Developers should always disclose any augmentations and alterations to users' representations, such as avatars, animated expressions, filters, or voice modifications, to maintain users' trust and awareness of the role played by digital mediation.
- 8. Transparency in Alteration of Bystanders, Personas and Avatars:* Developers should take steps to disclose and ensure that any alteration or augmentation of bystander appearances, personas, or avatars is done with consent if no other legal basis applies. Any alteration or augmentation should be respectful of human dignity and sensitive to the identities of others, while ensuring mitigation of potential risks or threats.

Article 7: Engagement with Non-Human Resources

1. *Altering Physical Environments:* Developers should engage with relevant stakeholders when altering properties of the physical environment through augmentation or digitalisation. These alterations should be respectful and sensitive to the social and cultural contexts of the objects and mitigate potential risks or threats (e.g., XR users and stakeholders present in the physical space).

2. *Transparency & Traceability:* Developers should provide mechanisms that allow users to easily distinguish between non-digital representations and digital creations such as human-driven entities and AI-driven entities, ensuring *transparency* in immersive environments. The transparent identification of AI agents as non-human entities and disclosing their purpose and capabilities should be provided. Additionally, developers should be able to trace the origins of digital assets and verify that the usage of digital assets in the virtual worlds does not violate the platforms' terms and conditions.

3. *Deployment of Socially-Interactive AI Agents:* Developers should assess and address the impact of socially-interactive AI agents on end-users, promoting supportive, non-exploitative interactions that prioritise user well-being. This includes promoting sincere identity by providing clear and understandable communication to the user about the nature of digital identities they encounter – human-driven entities or AI-driven entities. Users should retain autonomy through explicit consent mechanisms and control over their interactions with AI-driven entities.

Glossary

Accessibility: the usability of a product, service, environment or facility by people with the widest range of capabilities.²

Alteration: a change, usually a slight change, in the appearance, character, or structure of something.³

AI agent: advanced artificial intelligence systems that can complete a task or make a decision.⁴

Anonymity: refers to an individual not being identifiable within a set of subjects (e.g., by removing or altering identifiers in data). Therefore, anonymous data is not personal data.

Augmentation: A noun for any process or amount that makes something bigger or greater. Here, it refers to modifying an object, person or scene in the virtual world or adding digital objects to the real world in AR or MR applications.

Augmented Reality (AR): a type of reality technology that superimposes digital content onto the real world, enhancing perception but not replacing the real environment. Often achieved by using the camera on a smartphone or a wearable device.⁵

Avatar: a digital representation of a person or user within a virtual world. Avatars are customizable and can be designed to reflect aspects of the real self, an idealized self, or a completely fictional character.⁶

Biometric data: personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological, or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allows or confirms the unique identification of that natural person.⁷

Bystander: people within sensing range of the user of an immersive technology device.⁸

Digital identity: a collection of personal data that uniquely represents an individual or organisation in the digital world. Digital identity is used for authentication, authorisation and verification purposes

² International Organization for Standardization, *ISO 9241-171:2008: Ergonomics of human-system interaction—Part 171: Guidance on software accessibility* (2008), <https://www.iso.org/standard/39080.html>

³ Cambridge University Press, s.v. "Alteration," *Cambridge Dictionary*, accessed August 28, 2025, <https://dictionary.cambridge.org>

⁴ R. D. Caballar, "What Are AI Agents?" *IEEE Spectrum*, November 19, 2024, <https://spectrum.ieee.org/ai-agents>

⁵ European Commission. (n.d.). *Frequently asked questions (FAQ) on virtual worlds*. Shaping Europe's Digital Future. Retrieved August 28, 2025, from <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/faqs/frequently-asked-questions-faq-virtual-worlds>

⁶ European Commission, "Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) on Virtual Worlds," *Shaping Europe's Digital Future*, accessed August 28, 2025, <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/faqs/frequently-asked-questions-faq-virtual-worlds>

⁷ European Parliament and Council, **Regulation (EU) 2016/679** of 27 April 2016 (General Data Protection Regulation), *Official Journal of the European Union* L 119 (May 4, 2016), art. 4(14)

⁸ Joseph O'Hagan, Pejman Saeghe, Jan Gugenheimer, Daniel Medeiros, Karola Marky, Mohamed Khamis, and Mark McGill, "Privacy-Enhancing Technology and Everyday Augmented Reality: Understanding Bystanders' Varying Needs for Awareness and Consent," *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies* 6, no. 4 (2023): Article 177, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3569501>

online. It includes the digital footprints left behind while using digital services. In this Code it is considered singular; a person should only have one digital identity.⁹

Disembodiment: the subjective experience of lacking a body or being detached from the physical body.¹⁰

Embodiment: the subjective experience of owning a body, being located in space, and having a first-person perspective.¹¹

Human-centred design: an approach to interactive systems development that aims to make systems usable and useful by focusing on the users, their needs and requirements, and by applying human factors/ergonomics, and usability knowledge and techniques. This approach enhances effectiveness and efficiency, improves human well-being, user satisfaction, accessibility and sustainability; and counteracts possible adverse effects of use on human health, safety and performance.¹²

Identity: personal and/or social identity such as name, age, gender, nationality, ethnicity, cultural aspects. In this Code it is considered singular.

Immersive technologies: Technologies that either enhance or replace a real-world environment with simulated or virtual elements, delivering engaging, interactive, and personalized user experiences.¹³

Immersive Environment: Refers to a digital or simulated environment that completely surrounds the user, providing sensory engagement (visual, auditory, and/or tactile) such that the user perceives themselves as being within and interacting with that environment.

Interoperability: Moving from a set of independent platforms and services to an integrated network of real-time reality capture layer or 3D virtual worlds. Interoperability and interchange across servers and clients through existing and emerging standards, frameworks, and guidelines.¹⁴

Mixed Reality (MR): a type of immersive technology that merges real and virtual environments in a way that both physical and digital objects appear to coexist and interact in real time

Moral dilemmas: situations in which there is a conflict between moral requirements, and the moral agent cannot satisfy both.¹⁵

⁹ European Commission, “Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) on Virtual Worlds,” *Shaping Europe’s Digital Future*, s.v. “What is digital identity?,” accessed August 28, 2025, <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/faqs/frequently-asked-questions-faq-virtual-worlds>.

¹⁰ Michael Madary and Thomas K. Metzinger, “Real Virtuality: A Code of Ethical Conduct. Recommendations for Good Scientific Practice and the Consumer Protection of Virtual Reality Users,” *Frontiers in Robotics and AI* 3 (2016): Article 3, <https://doi.org/10.3389/frobt.2016.00003>

¹¹ Madary and Metzinger, “Real Virtuality,” Art. 3.

¹² International Organization for Standardization, *ISO 9241-210:2019: Ergonomics of human-system interaction—Part 210: Human-centred design for interactive systems* (Geneva: ISO, 2019), Introduction. <https://www.iso.org/standard/77520.html>

¹³ European Commission, “Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) on Virtual Worlds,” *Shaping Europe’s Digital Future*, accessed August 28, 2025, <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/faqs/frequently-asked-questions-faq-virtual-worlds>

¹⁴ Alina Kadlubsky, Sathiya Kumar, and Mikel Salazar, *D4.1: Map Existing and Emerging Requirements for Interoperability in XR and Spatial Computing* (XR4HUMAN project deliverable, 2023), PDF, https://xr4human.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/D4.1_Map-of-requirements_v02.pdf

¹⁵ Terrance C. McConnell, “Moral Dilemmas,” *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, accessed August 28, 2025, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/moral-dilemmas/>

Opt-in/ Opt-out: Opting in means that a user will take an affirmative action to offer their consent, whereas opting out means a user will take action to withdraw their consent.¹⁶

Persona: the character, image, or personality someone presents to others, often intentionally or as part of a specific context.

Personal data: Any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one which can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identify of that natural person.¹⁷

Private space: User-specific, controlled environment where interactions, data, and experiences are intended to be personal or restricted.

Public space: Shared, open environments where multiple users can interact, observe, or participate.

Sensitive data: personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic or biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying an individual, health data or data concerning an individual's sex life or sexual orientation.¹⁸

User: a natural person or entity that knowingly engages with or utilizes an immersive technology device/product/tool/service/platform.¹⁹

Virtual Reality (VR): the use of computer technology to create a simulated environment with which a user can interact through multi-sensory stimuli and responses. A digital environment that can be experienced and interacted with as if that environment were real.

eXtended Reality (XR): the collective term for immersive technologies such as Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR), along with any future variations these technologies may evolve into. It encompasses the entire spectrum of experiences that blend real and virtual environments, ranging from fully physical to fully digital worlds and all the combinations in between.²⁰

¹⁶ X Reality Safety Intelligence (XRSI), "Immersive Technology Standards," *XRSI—Human Intelligence in the Loop*, accessed August 28, 2025, <https://xrsi.org/publication/immersive-technology-standards>

¹⁷ European Parliament and Council. *Regulation (EU) 2016/679* of 27 April 2016 (General Data Protection Regulation). *Official Journal of the European Union* L 119 (May 4, 2016): 1–88. Article 4(1)

¹⁸ European Parliament and Council, *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR)*, art. 4(1).

¹⁹ International Organization for Standardization, *ISO 9241-210:2019: Ergonomics of Human-System Interaction—Part 210: Human-Centred Design for Interactive Systems* (Geneva: ISO, 2019), §3.14

²⁰ Paul Milgram and Fumio Kishino, "A Taxonomy of Mixed Reality Visual Displays," *IEICE Transactions on Information and Systems* E77-D, no. 12 (1994): 1321–1329, https://cs.gmu.edu/~zduric/cs499/Readings/r76JBo-Milgram_IEICE_1994.pdf

Annex A

XR4Human

Ethical Impact Assessment for Immersive Technologies

Authors: Shereen Cox, Lene A. Hagen

Reviewers: Rigmor Baraas, Rosemarie Bernabe, Alina Kadlubsky, Faisal Mushtaq, Oliver Schreer, Lucas Stephane

2025

Overview

The XR4human Ethical Impact Assessment (EIA) for Immersive Technologies aims to provide a structured framework for developers to assess, anticipate, and mitigate the effects of their innovations on users, society, and the environment. The ethics impact assessment serves as an essential tool for evaluating the ethical implications of immersive experiences, including virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR) based on the outlined principles and articles of the XR4human Code of Conduct for developers/users.

There are five (5) key areas of impact: Health and wellbeing, Autonomy and identity, Data and Technology, Social, and Environmental. The corresponding guiding principles and relevant articles from the XR4Human Code of Conduct are noted under each area of impact. The developer is encouraged to read the Code of Conduct before going through the questions in this impact assessment. Following this assessment, developers are encouraged to complete the checklist to ensure all areas have been considered.

Description of the XR experience

Please provide a brief description of the XR experience, including purpose, duration, and intended primary and secondary users. Additionally, describe the key features, the type of content presented, and the expected outcomes for the users.

Summary of the XR Experience

Impact Descriptor 1: Health and Wellbeing

[Guiding principle: Human Centred Design]

[Link: Article 4: [Wellbeing by Design](#)]

XR technologies can have both a positive and negative impact on health and wellbeing. The Code of Conduct seeks to address this by emphasizing a human-centred design approach.

Alignment with Human-Centred Design

1. How does the design prioritize user comfort, safety, and overall wellbeing throughout the experience?
2. Are the physical and mental health and wellbeing impacts balanced with other design goals, such as performance or realism?

Physical and Mental Wellbeing

This descriptor is focused on designing immersive experiences to maximise positive and minimise negative impacts on physical and mental health and wellbeing in the immersive experience.

1. Assessing user needs and context

1. Who are the primary and secondary users of the immersive experience?
2. How could the intended use e.g., duration, environment, or purpose of the immersive experience, impact physical and mental wellbeing?

3. Are there specific physical limitations among potential users that need to be addressed (e.g., visual impairment, limited mobility)? (Link: <https://www.w3.org>)
4. Does the immersive experience account for the diverse psychological needs of users, including those with mental health conditions or neurodiverse profiles?
5. How are users educated about the potential physical and mental health risks of immersive experience use and provided with clear guidelines for safe operation?

2. Assessing physical interaction design

1. Does the XR system account for ergonomic principles to minimize physical strain (e.g., weight of devices, repetitive motion)?
2. How does the design ensure comfort during prolonged use (e.g., adjustable headsets, lightweight materials)?
3. If head-mounted displays are used, are users allowed to adjust the head-mounted display to align with their interpupillary distance, fit their head size, and accommodate wearing prescription spectacles during use, to prevent visual discomfort?
4. Are users required to perform any physical actions that may lead to overexertion, strain, or unsafe conditions?

3. Physical safety and risk management

1. What measures are in place to prevent physical accidents or injuries during the immersive experience (e.g., collision warnings, safe zone boundaries)?
2. Does the system provide alerts or recommendations if users exceed safe usage limits (e.g., time warnings for prolonged sessions)?
3. Does the design include features that encourage regular breaks or movement to promote physical health?
4. Are there fail-safes or emergency protocols for users who may experience physical distress while immersed in the XR environment?
5. How does the immersive experience mitigate risks of cybersickness or vertigo caused by mismatched visual and vestibular cues?
6. Have you considered the long-term physical health implications due to prolonged use of the immersive experience and how it could contribute to musculoskeletal issues, such as neck strain or poor posture?

Psychological and cognitive impact:

This descriptor warns users about potential cognitive, emotional or psychological effects.

1. Does the XR experience intentionally evoke strong emotions (e.g., fear, excitement, empathy), and are those emotions appropriate for the context and audience?
2. How are potential triggers for anxiety, phobias, or post-traumatic stress mitigated in the design?
3. Does the XR experience provide users with clear, accessible ways to exit or pause the experience if they feel uncomfortable?
4. Are there risks of addiction or excessive engagement, and how are they addressed?

5. If AI is used in your XR experience, could the AI-driven personalization impact user behaviour, perception, and emotional responses?

Unique situations of vulnerability:

1. What age group is this experience suitable for according to local and regional regulations and standards?
2. Does this experience include scenes that may be considered frightening for younger users?
3. Is parental guidance recommended?
4. Does the immersive experience foster a safe and inclusive experience for vulnerable groups?

Impact Descriptor 2: Autonomy and Identity

[Guiding principles: Human-Centred Design; Identity and right to anonymity; Trustworthiness and Transparency]

[Link: Article 1: [User Transparency by Design](#); Article 5: [Identity](#); Article 6: [Engagement with Non-Human Resources](#)]

User Agency:

1. Does the immersive experience enable users to make meaningful choices about their actions and interactions?
2. Are there restrictions in the design (e.g., forced pathways, limited customization) that might undermine autonomy?
3. To what extent do AI-driven recommendations in immersive spaces shape user choices, and can this lead to manipulation or loss of independent thought?
4. Does the immersive experience respect user preferences for anonymity?
5. How does the XR system handle anonymity and accountability in multi-user settings?

Transparency:

1. Is the system transparent about how user data, preferences, and decisions are used within the immersive experience?
2. Are users adequately informed about the algorithms or AI that shape their immersive experiences?

Control:

1. Can users control how they interact with the environment (e.g., movement, interaction mechanics, or customization of settings)?
2. Are users able to pause, exit, or adjust the immersive experience when they feel uncomfortable or overwhelmed?
3. Are there mechanisms in place to allow users to override or opt out of AI-driven suggestions and interventions?
4. Are there safeguards to prevent AI-driven nudging from becoming manipulative, especially in persuasive or high-stakes scenarios?

5. Does the immersive experience offer mechanisms for users to report problems, suggest improvements or provide feedback on the application?

Consent:

1. How is informed consent addressed, particularly in collecting biometric data (e.g., eye tracking, body movements)?
2. Are users given clear and detailed options for opting into or out of data collection and system features?

Self-Representation and Diversity:

1. Does the XR system allow users to create and customize avatars or representations that align with their identity?
2. Are there adequate options for representing diverse identities, such as gender, ethnicity, and cultural symbols?

Identity Authenticity:

1. Can users maintain their real-world identity within the immersive experience, or are they forced to conform to predefined roles?
2. Are users given full creative control over their virtual identity, or does AI impose recommendations that might unconsciously shape their choices?
3. Are users allowed full control over their digital identity, including after death, with the possibility to customize and transfer them across platforms?
4. Are there safeguards to prevent identity theft or misrepresentation, such as deepfakes or unauthorized use of personal data?

Impact Descriptor 3: Data and Technology

[Guiding principles: Trustworthiness and Transparency; Privacy and Data governance; Technical security and Interoperability]

[Link: Article 2: [Data gathering protection and use](#)]

This descriptor focuses on the type of data collected by the immersive technology. It emphasizes the sensitivity of the data, helping users and, when relevant, bystanders to understand the potential privacy risk and whether the data is shared with third parties. Additionally, it considers the seamless exchange between technology systems while maintaining robust security protocols which would require a balance between efficiency, user trust, and compliance with ethical and legal standards.

Privacy and Data Governance

Data protection laws:

1. Does the XR application conform to laws and standards protecting privacy?

Data collection:

1. Does the immersive experience collect usage data and device information?
2. Does the immersive experience collect personal data, such as username or email?

3. Does the immersive experience use eye-tracking or record head movements?

Data sensitivity:

1. Does the immersive experience collect user sensitive biometric data, including heart rate and facial expressions?
2. Does the immersive experience record user location and interactions within the virtual environment?

Data sharing:

1. Does the XR application allow the sharing of user data with third parties without explicit consent?
2. If user data is shared, is the data anonymized to prevent re-identification?
3. Is there a risk that an individual may see personal information of another individual when using the XR system?

Data Governance

1. What measures are in place to protect user privacy and ensure secure handling of personal data in the immersive environment?
2. How does the system address concerns related to biometric data collection, such as eye tracking or body movement analysis?
3. Are users fully informed about how their data is being collected, stored, used, and shared?
4. Do users have the right to access, modify or delete their data?
5. Is user data processed on-device, wherever feasible, to minimise exposure to security risks?

Technical Security

1. What measures are in place to safeguard user data (e.g., encryption, secure data storage)?
2. What are the technical measures to ensure compliance with data protection regulations and informational security standards (e.g., GDPR)?
3. What steps have been taken to identify and address potential vulnerabilities in the system?
4. Are regular security audits or penetration tests conducted to ensure system integrity?
5. How does the system detect and mitigate unauthorized access or cyberattacks?
6. Are security updates and patches communicated and deployed promptly?
7. What mechanisms are in place to allow users to report security issues or breaches?
8. Does the system include fail-safes to prevent service interruptions during security incidents?
9. How are backup and recovery plans implemented to protect against data loss or system downtime?
10. Are there protocols for handling large-scale breaches or significant vulnerabilities?
11. How does the system prevent the misuse of immersive technology for unethical purposes, such as surveillance or manipulation?

Interoperability

1. Does the XR system support seamless integration with other platforms, devices, or applications?
2. Which standards are implemented?
3. How does the system handle data exchange between different formats, protocols, or devices?
4. Are there any compatibility issues with legacy systems or emerging technologies?
5. How scalable is the system for integrating with future technologies or platforms?
6. Are users able to switch between devices or environments without losing functionality or progress?
7. Are there usability challenges or inconsistencies when the system is used across multiple platforms?
8. How does the system handle interruptions or failures in cross-platform integration?
9. How does the system ensure compatibility with evolving industry standards and protocols?
10. Are updates or new integrations likely to disrupt existing functionality?
11. Does the system allow for easy adaptation to new devices, software, or platforms?
12. What processes are in place to identify and address emerging interoperability needs?

Impact Descriptor 4: Social

[Guiding Principles: Diversity, Inclusivity and Accessibility, Equitability; Safe Experience; Risk Management and Moral Dilemma Resolution]

[Link: Article 6: [Shared Spaces](#); Article 7: [Engagement with Non-Human Resources](#)]

This descriptor highlights broader societal implications of the technology. It explains the nature and extent of social interaction within the immersive experience. It outlines the physical, sensory, and cognitive abilities required to use the immersive technology effectively and any accessibility features available within the immersive experience.

Accessibility:

1. Is the immersive experience designed to accommodate users with diverse physical or mental/cognitive abilities or disabilities?
2. How does the experience accommodate users with different levels of physical mobility or fitness?
3. How does the system provide alternate interaction methods for users who may find standard mechanisms (e.g., controllers or gestures) challenging?
4. Are there language-neutral features that enhance accessibility for a broad audience?
5. Does the application support subtitles and closed captions?
6. Does the experience offer alternative input methods for users with mobility limitations?

7. Does the application support adjustable text size and screen settings, text-to-speech, audio descriptions, or screen readers?
8. Can the XR system be used in both standing and seated modes, and are controls customizable for ease of use?
9. Is user information provided in multiple formats (e.g., audio/video) to be comprehensible to the broadest range of users?

Social interaction management:

1. Does this experience allow the user to interact with others in shared immersive spaces?
2. Are there clear distinctions between private and shared spaces within the immersive environment?
3. Does the application have clear community guidelines for behaviour within shared immersive spaces, that promote respect, inclusivity, and safety for all participants?
4. Can users block or mute others if necessary?
5. Does the application have a system to monitor social interactions to ensure a respectful environment and remove abusive or harmful content?
6. Are there features to prevent or address harmful social behaviours, such as abuse, harassment or bullying in shared immersive spaces?
7. Does the application have built-in reporting tools to address any inappropriate behaviour?
8. Does the XR technology enable users to report harmful behaviours in shared immersive spaces?
9. How does the system impact users' sense of belonging, community, or social roles in shared immersive spaces?
10. Are there mechanisms to address discrimination, stereotyping, or identity-based harassment in multi-user settings?

Potential for misuse:

1. Can this technology be used for surveillance or data collection without the user's knowledge?
2. Does the application allow for user-generated content, which may include harmful or offensive material?
3. How does the system prevent misuse, such as creating or spreading harmful content within shared immersive spaces?

Social implications:

1. Does the cost of the XR hardware or software create barriers for certain socioeconomic groups?

2. How does the design consider the needs of users from different cultural, linguistic, or geographic backgrounds
3. Does the XR content respect and represent cultural diversity and avoid stereotypes or biases?
4. How are local or community voices included in the design process, especially for culturally sensitive applications?
5. Are there risks of cultural appropriation or misrepresentation in the content or interactions enabled by the XR system?
6. Does the technology support meaningful connections between users, or does it risk promoting isolation?

Transparency in shared immersive spaces:

1. Are actions that may be invisible to other users in shared immersive spaces, such as recording or capturing screenshots, clearly communicated to all users?
2. Are users clearly informed when AI algorithms modify their representation in shared immersive environments, such as by generating animated expressions based on detected or predicted emotions or applying visual filters that alter their appearance?

Impact Descriptor 5: Environmental

[Guiding Principle: Sustainability]

[Link: Article 3: [Risk Management by Design](#)]

1. Does the XR technology comply with environmental regulations and sustainability standards?
2. Are there certifications (e.g., Energy Star, EPEAT) that verify the environmental friendliness of the XR devices or systems?
3. Are there opportunities to optimize energy efficiency in device design and software performance?
4. Are there measures in place to use renewable energy sources for powering the XR system?

Ethical impact of the XR experience

The intent of this Ethical Impact Assessment (EIA) is to provide the developer with an opportunity to examine the potential ethical implications of the proposed or existing XR experience, with a focus on its alignment with the ethical principles of the XR4Human Code of Conduct, regulatory frameworks, and best practices in extended reality (XR) development.

Based on your reflection and responses to the key areas of impact outlined in this assessment, and using the checklist provided (Annex B), please provide a summary overview of how your project aligns with the key ethical considerations relevant to its development and deployment.

Overview based on the XR4human checklist. Please state the areas that comply in full, in part and not applicable. Also indicate the reasons, if applicable, where you consider some things as not fully aligned. Also indicate any other risk areas of concern that has not been addressed in the EIA.

Annex B

XR4HUMAN Human-Centered and Ethical Development of Immersive Technologies Checklist

Authors: Shereen Cox, Lene A. Hagen

Reviewers: Rigmor Baraas, Rosemarie Bernabe, Alina Kadlubsky, Faisal Mushtaq, Oliver Schreer, Lucas Stephane

2025

The XR4HUMAN Human-Centered and Ethical Development of Immersive Technologies Checklist is designed to help assess compliance with the principles and articles of the Code of Conduct. For more precise references and guidance, please consult the Code of Conduct directly. Before using this checklist for review, it is recommended to review the Code of Conduct and complete the ethical impact assessment.

Key Areas of Impact	Yes	No	In-part	N/A	Evidence / Notes to indicate criterion is satisfied
1. Health and Wellbeing					
Principles: Human-Centered Design Articles: Wellbeing by Design					
The XR experience was developed through iterative user testing and ethical design principles, ensuring that it aligns with human-centered design criteria by prioritizing usability and user well-being (physical and mental).					
2. Autonomy and Identity					
Principles: Human-Centred Design; Identity and right to anonymity; Trustworthiness and Transparency Articles: User Transparency by Design; Identity; Engagement with Non-Human Resources					
The XR experience was designed to authentically represent user identities while upholding autonomy, ensuring that users have full control over their presence, choices, and interactions within the immersive environment.					
3. Data and Technology					
Principles: Trustworthiness and Transparency; Privacy and Data governance; Technical security and interoperability Articles: Data gathering protection and use					
Privacy and Data Governance: The XR experience was developed with robust data protection measures and adherence to legal and ethical data governance frameworks, ensuring user privacy, informed consent, and secure handling of personal data.					
Interoperability: The XR experience was developed with consideration of interoperability to facilitate seamless integration across platforms where practicable.					
Technical security: Technical security measures include robust cybersecurity measures to protect user data and system integrity.					
4. Social					
Principles: Diversity, inclusivity and accessibility, Equitability; Safe Experience; Risk Management and Moral Dilemma Resolution Articles: Shared Spaces; Engagement with Non-Human Resources					
Equitability and Diversity: The XR experience was developed with a commitment to social equity, ensuring fair representation, inclusive design, and equitable access to immersive technologies for diverse users, where practicable.					
Accessibility and Inclusivity: The XR experience was designed with accessibility and inclusivity at its core, incorporating adaptive features, diverse user needs, and compliance with accessibility standards to facilitate equitable participation for all users.					
5. Environmental					
Principles: Sustainability Articles: Risk Management by Design					
The XR experience was developed with sustainability in mind, incorporating energy-efficient technologies, eco-friendly design practices, and responsible resource engagement to minimize environmental impact.					

